

ISic002990

I.Sicily inscription 002990

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Francesca Prado,system

Autopsy

2006.04

Last Change

2021-07-08 - Francesca Prado edited the text, tagged named entities and added English and Italian translation

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance

Original discovery not recorded.

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Centuripe, Museo Archeologico Regionale di Centuripe

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 20.5 cm

Width 32 cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Στάτια □ Ἄνθη □
3. χρη[στά] χαῖ [ρεῖζησ]εν
5. [ἔτη ---]

Apparatus

Text after Libertini 1949

Translation (en)

Farewell worthy Statia Anthe! She lived...

Translation (it)

Addio, degna Statia Anthe! Ella visse...

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645340

EDR 146666

EDCS 70900397

URI <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic002990>
DOI [10.5281/zenodo.4387877](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4387877)

Bibliography

undefined, undefined 1888-. Bulletin épigraphique. *Bulletin épigraphique*. At 1953.0279

Libertini, G 1949. Iscrizioni Centuripine. *Siculorum Gymnasium*. 2: 91-97. At 95 no.1 fig.3

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2021-07-14): ISic002990. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5104391>